

Genetic resources of GEB24

S. R. S. Rangasamy, S. Palanisamy, W. W. Manuel, S. M. Lal, and K. Natarajamoorthy, Plant Breeding Station (PBS), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

GEB24, also called Kitchili Samba, selected from the Andhra Pradesh local variety Konamani, was released in 1921. It is tall (120-135 cm), has 150-d duration, and is highly photoperiod sensitive. It tillers profusely, with nonshattering grain. Despite its relatively low yield potential (3.5 t/ha), it is popular mainly for its very good quality rice. Its grain is medium slender and white.

GEB24 has been used extensively in several national and international breeding programs and several modern high-yielding varieties carry its genes.

It is the ultimate maternal progenitor of 18 varieties (see figure). Eight varieties released between 1945 and 1975 are direct derivatives: TKM6 is resistant to stem borer (SB); Co 30 is resistant to blast; co 31 (the fit outcome of interspecific cross) is resistant to drought. Ten varieties released between 1970 and 1983 are second-generation derivatives: Ratna is noted for SB resistance and Punjab Basmati 1, for scented rice.

Derivatives with GEB24 as maternal progenitor.

A list of 83 varieties with GEB24 features inherited paternally is available from the authors. They include 23 from

Tamil Nadu, 20 from other Indian states, 28 from IRRI, and 12 from other countries. □

Masuli, most popular rice variety in Nepal

G. L. Shrestha, National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur Agriculture Station, Bara, Nepal

Rice in Nepal occupies 59% of the total cultivated land and contributes 52% of the total edible food grain. Rice employs more than 75% of the population (17.5 million) at least 6 mo a year and contributes 23% of the total gross domestic product (GDP).

In 1987, the total rice area was 1.4 million ha, production was 3 million t, with average yield of 2.1 t/ha (see table).

Of the 31 improved rice varieties

Area, production, and productivity of rice in different ecological regions of Nepal in 1987 (Food and Agricultural Marketing Department, Lalitpur, Nepal, 1988).

Ecological region	Area		Production		Productivity (t/ha)
	ha	%	ha	%	
Tarai	1,049,900	73.7	2,249,090	75.2	2.1
Mid-hill	337,890	23.8	667,390	22.3	2.0
High hill	35,500	2.5	65,300	2.5	1.8
Total	1,423,290	100.0	2,981,340	100.0	2.1

(national average)

Nepal has released during the last 20 yr, Masuli, released in 1973, is the most popular in the subtropical climatic region of Tarai, inner Tarai, and similar climatic river basin areas and valleys up to 900-m altitude. In 1987, more than

50% of the total ricelands were planted to improved varieties; Masuli covered 26.6% of the total, more than 379,506 ha. Market surveys indicate that at least 60% of the milled rice marketed in the country is Masuli.